

Evaluation of Social Media as an Example of Elements Affecting Human Personality Structures

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Abstract

The Most Frequent Varieties of Personality Types One example of a variety of personality types is the so-called "type A" and "type B" personality hypotheses. People who are easygoing and tranquil fall into the Type B group, whereas those who are impatient and achievement-oriented belong to the Type A category. This assertion, which was first made by the theory, has not been borne up by the findings of empirical investigations even though it was initially said that persons with a personality type A are at a larger risk for coronary heart disease (CHD). Those whose personalities fall into the type A category are more likely to suffer from personality disorders, while those whose personalities fall into the type B category are more likely to get dependent on alcohol. These conclusions come from a research. Occasionally, for the sake of convenience, trait theorists may use the phrase "type" to refer to a person who has an unusually high or low score on a certain personality feature. This can be done in a variety of contexts. According to Hans Eysenck, higher-order personality variables are referred to as types, while traits refer to more particular personality characteristics that are connected. Meyer Friedman, a cardiologist, and Ray Rosenman, a psychologist, were the first people to recognize behaviors linked with type A personality as a potential risk factor for heart disease. They made this discovery in the 1950s.

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Friedman and Rosenman determined that healthy persons had a risk of coronary heart disease that was twice as high when they looked at the findings of an eight-and-a-half-year study of healthy males between the ages of 35 and 59. The research participants were all men. They gave off the idea of being relaxed and reflective, but in truth, they were agitated and thrilled about the situation. Individuals whose personalities suit the description of the Type A personality are outgoing, ambitious, highly organized, extremely status conscious, sensitive, impatient, irritable, initiative-taking, and interested in getting the most out of their time management skills. Individuals who have personality types A and A tend to be "workaholics" who are always trying to improve themselves. They put a lot of pressure on themselves to achieve deadlines since they despise being late and the inability to decide how they feel. Individuals who have personalities with a Type A tend to report greater levels of stress regarding their professions, as well as poorer levels of overall job satisfaction. Those who have the Type B personality are quite different from those who have the Type A personality. Those who have a personality type B are, by definition, thought to have lower levels of stress in their life than those with other personality types. They often have a set work schedule and can take satisfaction in their accomplishments, but they are more prone to disregard the physical or mental strain that is brought on by falling short of their objectives. They are less concerned with winning or losing than their Type A counterparts, and more focused with just enjoying the game, regardless of whether they win or lose. This contrasts with Type A counterparts, who are more concerned with achieving success. In contrast to the rhythm of multitasking employment that is typical of people with Type A personalities, people with Type B personalities are more likely to gravitate toward creative professions such as writing, consulting, therapy, acting, and acting. This is because people with Type B personalities tend to be more imaginative. On the other side, those who work in education, the judicial system, and administration of computer networks and systems are more likely to have Type B personalities.

Keywords: *Human Personality Structures, Personality Theories, Social Media and Personality, Social Media, Human Personality*

Introduction

It's probable that each of their unique personalities enjoys venturing into uncharted territory with novel ideas and notions. A person who has a typical Type C personality seems emotionless, is often incapable of expressing themselves, and strives to ensure the comfort of others around them. A person is said to have a Type D personality if they have a propensity for negative affect (such as anxiety, anger, and sadness) and social inhibition; this is a notion that is used in medical psychology (eg, silence and lack of self-confidence). The letter D stands for the word "distressed," which is an adjective. Individuals whose personalities fit the criteria of Type D are more likely to suffer an increase in the frequency and intensity of negative feelings as time and experience passes. These individuals also have a propensity to keep these sentiments to themselves out of concern that others would disapprove of them or reject them. The idea was conceived by Johan Denollet, a professor of medical psychology at Tilburg University in Tilburg, the Netherlands. His inspiration came from clinical observations, empirical data, and existing ideas of personality in cardiac patients.

Among cardiac patients, the proportion of persons who have the personality type D ranges from 18% to 53%, although the overall occurrence of this personality type is 21% in the general population [4]. As a result of their influencing character, people with the I Personality Type do not mind being the focus of attention and do not try to avoid it. They have a lot of energy, are upbeat, conversational, and convincing, yet at the same time they are impetuous and emotional. This kind of personality has an innate sense of trust in other people, takes immense pleasure in being among other people, and achieves their best results when they are collaborating with others or participating in group activities.

Those who have type A do not necessarily all have an increased risk of having heart disease. A psychologist named Suzanne Kabasa has provided an analysis of a personality type that she calls the bold personality (Type H). People who have personalities of the type H variety vary in three ways from people who have personalities of the type A variety and from those who are more vulnerable to the adverse effects of stress. People who are classified as Type H have a strong conviction that it is their moral duty to remain true to their most fundamental ideals and convictions.

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Method

The hunt for a definition, classification, and explanation of what personality is, which is what affects how we think, perceive, feel, and behave, has been a mystery up until now. Although probably more is known about personality disorders than about normal personality, the search for a theory that can clearly delineate the factors that contribute to personality continues, despite the fact that it is likely that more is known about personality disorders than about normal personality. The research that has been done up to this point does not seem to have produced any findings that are persuasive, and our understanding of what makes up a normal personality is always expanding. The concept of a person's personality is so intriguing that it's almost difficult not to be captivated by it.

- *How is it that two people can act in such diverse ways and arrive at such different conclusions even though their DNA is more than 99.999 percent identical?*

Even siblings who are raised in the same environment or in one that is relatively close to it might develop into persons who have personalities that may not be all that unlike from one another even after they have reached adulthood. Even when dealing with a single individual, understanding someone's personality might be challenging. Because of this, many of us feel the need to participate in personality tests to get a more in-depth knowledge of who we are and the reasons we are the way that we are. Just like the rest of us, psychologists are captivated by personality, and they utilize scientific study to attempt to answer the questions that the rest of us have about personality.

The study of the psychological similarities and differences that are shared by different persons is the focus of a distinct topic within the discipline of psychology known as personality psychology. Most significantly, it tries to describe the psychological processes that are responsible for the development of the one-of-a-kind personality that each person has. On the other hand, research into people's personalities is a lot more involved than the straightforward personality quizzes you could see in a magazine.

Theories Concerning the Characteristics of People

The following are three of the most widely disseminated personality theories, along with some instances of how these theories might be used in day-to-day life and their ramifications.

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Freud's Theory

Anybody who is serious about getting a formal education in psychology should be conversant with Sigmund Freud's concepts since psychoanalysis dramatically transformed the way people manage mental disease. The fact that he possesses a well-developed and all-encompassing theory of personality is not something that ought to come as much of a surprise to anybody. Freud theorized that the creation of a person's personality was dependent on inborn urges, unconscious processes, and the influences exerted on a kid while they were young. Because of this, Freud concluded that the first five years of a person's existence are generally the most important in determining their personality. As a kid progresses through Freud's five psychosexual stages—namely oral, anal, phallic, occult, and genital, in that order—certain characteristics of their personalities begin to emerge. For instance, a kid who is overfed during the oral phase will have a personality that is aggressive and domineering, while a child who is undernourished during this age would develop a personality that is submissive and reliant on others. If the toilet training of an anal kid is done too softly, the child will be too generous and clumsy, but if it is done too strictly, the child will become obsessive and defiant.

Id, Ego, and Psyche Are Three Aspects of Personality Developed During Childhood

The psyche, the ego, and the id are the three components of a person's personality that emerge throughout infancy. The id is the instinctual, idealistic personality; the psyche is the personality that applies the values and morals gained by society; and the ego is the personality that balances these impulses to produce a balanced and happy personality.

The imbalances result in psychosis and neurosis, which are characteristics of personality from which Freud attempted to rescue his patients by returning to the psychosexual phases of analysis. Getting suitable medical therapy might be tough.

Hans Eysenck's Theory of Personality

Hans Eysenck's theory of personality is simpler, more accessible, and more accurate than Freud's, even though Freud is more well-known among the public. Psychologists may utilize a standardized test that was designed by Eysenck to discover known features of a patient's personality to evaluate a patient's mental health using the test. In the end, Eysenck believed personality is nothing more

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than an expression of the neurological system, and he believed that a person may build a healthy personality by striking a balance between the stimulation and repression of their nerves. In the years after the conclusion of World War II, Eysenck created a series of questions for the purpose of identifying mental disease among returning service members who were being treated for neurotic disorders at the time. Eysenck developed first-order personality characteristics by drawing similarities between the responses of the soldiers and his own observations of those responses. He discovered a great deal of shared ground.

This category includes traits such as irritation, composure, impulsiveness, pessimism, passivity, and liveliness, amongst others. After doing more study, Eysenck was able to determine the two major dimensions, commonly referred to as quadratic personality characteristics, which are important for shaping an individual's personality and how they interact with other people. Two of these personality types are extraversion, and the other two are introversion and neuroticism. Constancy and extraversion are the other two. Both extraversion and introversion are used to characterize a subject's social conduct, whereas neuroticism and stability are used to describe the subject's capacity to regulate their emotions. After some time, Eysenck expanded his concept to include a third stage that he named psychoticism. Those who fall under this category are characterized by a lack of empathy and a harsh and aggressive disposition. It is possible to modify some parts of one's personality via the process of retraining the neural system to react differently to stress. One way to do this is through cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT).

[Cattell's 16-Point Frequency Factor Feature Theory](#)

Raymond Cattell's theory of personality was in striking opposition to the research conducted by Eysenck. Cattell sought to reject the notion that personality only reflects three dimensions, therefore he set out to demonstrate that to understand personality, one needs take into consideration a significantly wider number of attributes. He was successful in doing so. Cattell conducted research on a huge and varied group of people to accomplish this goal. She then sorted the massive quantity of material she gathered into the following categories: L-data, which includes information on a person's life history such as their grades in school and their success on the job; Q-data, which contains information about routine surveys; and T-data, which includes test results (objective

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tests). Cattell came up with a grand total of sixteen different characteristics of people's personalities in the end.

This category includes characteristics such as intelligence, sensitivity, independence, vigor, and warmth. After that, he classified them into source characteristics and surface characteristics, which are more difficult and easier to identify, respectively, but are more vital and less useful when attempting to characterize an individual's personality. These ideas and hypotheses about human nature have been categorized into a variety of distinct viewpoints ever since Sigmund Freud laid the groundwork for the practice.

It is essential to acknowledge that the personality theorists of the previous century did not place a significant emphasis on the significance of racial and cultural distinctions. As we will see, it does not make sense to generalize, say, the ideas of one theorist based on clinical observations of neurotic European women, or the ideas of another theorist based on tests given to male American college students, to all people. For instance, the ideas of one theorist are based on clinical observations of neurotic European women. Because of this, although we will be addressing the research on these ideas and illustrating how they might be applied in real-life diagnostic and treatment issues, we will also aim to highlight how characteristics such as age, gender, and race can also be beneficial.

There are several factors that may play a role in one's level of influence, including their ethnicity, nationality, religious views, and sexual orientation. To suggest that the personality you were born with is one of the most significant aspects of your life is not an exaggeration by any means. Not only has it been a factor in the development of your experiences up to this point, but it will also continue to be one for the rest of your life. Everything you've done up to this point, everything you intend for the future, whether or not you'll be a good spouse, spouse, spouse, or father, and even your physical state may be influenced by your personality as well as the qualities of the people who are in your immediate environment. Personality may restrict or broaden the range of choices and opportunities presented in life. It can also prevent you from engaging in certain pursuits or make it possible for you to get the most possible value from the experiences you do have. As a

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direct consequence of it, the lives of some people are constrained, confined, and hindered in some way, whilst for others, it has opened a whole new universe of opportunities and possibilities.

Literature Review

Based on data that can be found in published works, it has been suggested that the study of personality can be divided into three main approaches:

- (1) *Constructivism,*
- (2) *Situationism and*
- (3) *Interactionism*

It has type theories, trait theories, and factor theories, which are the three main classes of personality theories, been noticed that the employment of these approaches has led to the establishment of these three major classifications of personality theories. It was also stated that even though extroversion/introversion and risk-taking are the two most crucial factors, other personality factors such as tolerance for ambiguity, empathy, self-esteem, shyness, and intelligence are also addressed. This was stated even though these are the two most crucial factors. On the other hand, it was said that intellect was the most crucial component. Personality may be described as "the person's knowledge of his or her own qualities that disclose the aspects of the individual," as stated by Hjelle (1992). It is also an extremely efficient approach for gaining the freedom to build one's own identity while simultaneously adjusting to the circumstances of life on a global scale. Although though intellect and personality are completely distinct from one another, people often make the mistake of thinking that the former is a component of the latter. This is since intelligence has such a huge influence on a person's personality.

The idea of personality may be comprehended from a variety of distinct viewpoints, the most typical of which are the psychodynamic viewpoint, the behavioral viewpoint, the learning perspective, and the trait viewpoint.

The classic viewpoint of personality psychology is referred to as the trait perspective (Abend, 1983). According to the findings of the study he referenced, it has been known since the time of

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the Greek culture that people have distinctive psychological characteristics in addition to their physical characteristics. This technique generates systems that identify and classify psychological traits, highlighting the disparities that might emerge between people when they are put in various contexts via the process. The methodology that is referred to as trait places an emphasis on the dispositional viewpoint, but it also investigates a wide variety of kinds and/or temperaments of persons by analyzing the traits they possess. Yet, under this specific viewpoint, terms such as characteristics, types, and predisposition are used interchangeably, even though the dispositional view of personality is the only one in which personality types and traits are constituents. The dispositional perspective of personality places an emphasis on the attributes that people already possess and that define them, including features of their brains and character. Personality characteristics are a useful tool for analyzing the ways in which people think, feel, and act throughout their lives. These variations may be traced back to the individual's unique experiences. Extroversion, introversion, and emotional stability are just some of the personality characteristics that can be used to classify individuals into one of many distinctive character traits. These characteristics are determined by an individual's personality as well as the traits that make up their personality. There are those with personalities that are categorized as type A, and then there are those with personalities that are categorized as type B. An individual's patterns of behavior, thoughts, and emotions may be categorized using the term "personality type," which is sometimes used interchangeably with "personality type." (Hogan, 1998) Strengths and Weaknesses (Leary, 1983) argues that the predisposition perspective of personality has several problems as well as several positives. Both arguments may be found in Hogan's (1998) Strengths and Weaknesses (Leary, 1983). The supply of useful instruments for use in the assessment process as well as the characterization of the individual's personality are included among its values. One other advantage is that it makes it possible to evaluate people of varying personality types. A lot of specialists whose work has concentrated on this point of view have come to the same conclusions because of their investigations, which have shown that an approach that is based on characteristics is beneficial. It is possible to draw comparisons between various persons thanks to the trait viewpoint, which also offers a scientific technique that enables personality research to be done in an impartial manner.

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The characteristic point of view is fallacious since it does not explain the mechanisms by which personality operates; instead, it only labels the event. This viewpoint does not provide a thorough explanation of the origins of the characteristics; rather, it proceeds to explicitly describe and categorize those characteristics. These theorists regularly detect the non-behavior-related traits that constitute part of the research for this viewpoint, but the inconsistency of behavior has been a big obstacle for those who study this perspective because of how the research for this perspective is structured.

Because factor analysis is used to make arbitrary judgements regarding the presence of features, this has led to the development of several theories that offer alternative approaches of achieving comparable outcomes. As a direct consequence of this, there is a lack of unambiguous explanation of the constituent parts that constitute the qualities, which has led to misunderstanding. Another drawback is that it is not amazingly effective at forecasting the future, and it does not provide any explanation as to the reasons behind the various behaviors that people exhibit in various settings. This is a major limitation of the model.

A New Way of Seeing

In the context of the debate between nature and nurture, the learning viewpoint has been considered, and it maintains that the latter has a greater impact on an individual's development (Buss, 1984). The learning viewpoint, when applied to another debate between the person and the circumstances, takes the side of the circumstances. In this setting, it is generally accepted that a person's personality is made up of characteristics that they have picked up throughout the course of their lifetime. The relationship between behaviorist and social psychology concepts that are prevalent in the world is shown by this learning viewpoint. Despite this, it functions according to its own set of principles, which among other things include social norms, modeling, and reinforcement. These are only few instances among many more. From this point of view, the history of a person as well as the characteristics that make them unique may contribute to the development, improvement, and modification of their personality. The learning perspective asserts that individuals pick up new behaviors because of the interactions and experiences they have with the environment in which they find themselves. This idea forms the foundation of the learning viewpoint. Yet, it recognizes the reality of reactions to stimulants, instincts, and the want to avoid

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negative events. According to this view, there is nothing written in stone about humans (Parsons, 1964).

Findings

The myriad of influences and factors that go into the making of a person's personality will be the subject matter of the area of research that we will be concentrating on. These concerns include whether we are born with a fixed personality type or inherit it from our parents, whether or if our personalities are influenced by influences that are unconscious to us, and whether our personalities change as we get older. Psychologists never give up on their quest to fit the pieces of the jigsaw together to paint a clearer and more accurate picture of what makes us who we are and how our perspective of the world around us develops.

Perspectives on Personality

Previously, we had a conversation regarding personality descriptions that are more scientific in nature. Let's take a look, now that we've examined how the phrase is defined in the dictionary, at how it's utilized in the activities and discussions that we engage in on a daily basis. This is a phrase that is often used while characterizing other people, including ourselves. When we use the word "I" in a phrase, a psychologist believes that if we examine our meaning, we may obtain a reasonably clear picture of what it means or what we intend by using the word "I." This is the argument made by the psychologist (Adams, 1954). When you refer to yourself with the "I" pronoun, you are providing a concise summary of all the information you need to know about yourself, including your worries, virtues, strengths, and shortcomings. You are an autonomous entity who is set aside from everyone else, and the word "I" is what makes this differentiation between you and the rest of the people.

How Others See Us

Studying the origins of a person's personality is another technique that may be taken to solving the issue. This idiom may be traced all the way back to about the year 1500 when it first appeared. It originates from the Roman term persona, which literally translates to "mask," and it is used to describe anything that players put on when they are participating in a game. It is not difficult to see how the noun "persona" came to be used to refer to our visible appearance, also known as our

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public face, which we portray to others who are located within our immediate vicinity. When we think about where the word "personality" came from, we may deduce that it refers to characteristics that are evident to other people or aspects of ourselves that are identifiable to other people. This is what we mean when we say that others can recognize our personalities. If this were the case, then people's perceptions of our personalities would be based on the impressions we provided to other people and how we seemed to them. According to this point of view, the most notable facet of a person's character is their personality because of the influence that they have on the lives of other people. To put it another way, our personalities may very well be the masks we put on while we are dealing with other people.

But is that all that comes to mind when we talk about personality?

When we talk about combining the many distinct aspects of a person, we are talking about that person's totality, which can be thought of as a collection of innumerable characteristics that go deeper than their superficial physical features. When we talk about a person's totality, we are talking about their totality. However, the phrase incorporates a broad range of abstract social and psychological qualities, some of which we may not be able to perceive clearly, which another person may attempt to conceal from us, and which we may try to hide from others.

Consistent and Predictable Attributes

When we discuss a person's personality, we are often referring to the persistent attributes that characterize that individual. Our working hypothesis is that a person's personality will remain relatively stable and recognized throughout their lifetime. For instance, even though we acknowledge that a friend may be level-headed most of the time, we are aware that on sometimes, the same person may have feelings of agitation, fear, or panic. As a direct consequence of this, our sense of identity may shift in accordance with the conditions at any given moment. Yet, despite its lack of rigidity, it is often resistive to rapid shifts in direction. In the 1960s, the discipline of psychology was rife with dispute over the relative importance of persistent human attributes, such as qualities and ambitions, on behavior, against the influence of conditioned variables (see Mischel, 1968, 1973). It wasn't until almost twenty years later that researchers came to the conclusion that "the long-standing and disputed dichotomy between the influence of the circumstance and the effect of the person on behavior is and has always been erroneous." The

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heated discussion was finally put to rest because of this admission for some time (Funder, 2001, p. 200). As a result, the issue was solved by adopting an interactionist methodology; this indicates that it was decided that enduring and stable personal characteristics, changing aspects of the situation, and the interaction between them must all be considered to provide a solution. Consequently, the problem was resolved by adopting an interactionist methodology.

Distinctive Features

It is probable that our notion of personality also includes the idea that distinguishes one individual from every other. Although we are aware that people have many similarities, we are also conscious of the fact that each of us is a one-of-a-kind person who has qualities that distinguish us from the other people. In conclusion, we may make the case that personality is an ever-present and one-of-a-kind collection of characteristics that is susceptible to change because of a wide range of experiences. Notwithstanding this definition, however, not all psychologists can reach a consensus over the meaning of the word "psychologist." It is vital, if we are to acquire a greater degree of clarity, to investigate what each personality theorist means by the term "this word." As we will see in the next discussion, everyone provides a unique interpretation of the core components that comprise personality, a particular viewpoint that develops into its own definition.

The Relationship Between Personality and Social Media

There has been a substantial amount of study done recently because of the ever-increasing and virtually continual usage of different social media platforms to engage with other people in a virtual world rather than in person.

There are at least three distinct ways in which an individual's personality and their usage of social media may interact to influence each other, which can ultimately lead to three issues for which psychologists are increasingly looking for answers.

Argument

According to the results of the study (Gosling, Gaddis, & Vazire, 2007; Back et al., 2010), the researchers concluded that the personality descriptions observed on the Internet are at least as accurate as those communicated in face-to-face interviews. On the other hand, the results of a more recent and in-depth research that was conducted in Germany suggest that many individuals tend

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to depict themselves on the internet as being far more balanced than they really are (Blumer & Doring, 2012). According to the findings of other, more recent studies, people who are introverted, neurotic, lonely, and socially disturbed find it easier to express their inner selves (their true personality) online rather than face-to-face. This is because the internet is a more anonymous and less judgmental environment (Marriott & Buchanan, 2014). Those who have a more favorable opinion of themselves have been demonstrated to be more active on social media sites like Facebook and others than those who do not have such a great perception of themselves. This can be seen in comparison to persons who do not have a positive perception of themselves (Seidman, 2014).

According to the findings of several studies, more women than men take selfies online. Taking an excessive number of selfies might make a person less likable and even lessen the intimacy or closeness of friendships. They may even encourage the notion that a person's outward look is more significant than their actual conduct while they are hanging out with pals in the real world (Drexler, 2013; Rutledge, 2013). You are aware that when we meet new people who we want to impress, such as a date or a possible job, we are not always honest about how we individually represent ourselves. One example of this would be lying about our education level. This is particularly important to keep in mind while we are attempting to create a favorable impression on a particular individual. When we are around individuals we have known for a long, who make us feel comfortable and who do not constitute a threat to us, our inclination to do something we did not really do may lessen. These people make us feel safe and do not pose a threat to us. As compared to the audience that can be reached via our typical offline lives, the audience that can be produced through social networking sites can be made considerably more quickly and in much greater quantity. One may argue that this is the single most significant difference. In addition, we now know that what we share about ourselves on social media can have significant potential repercussions on both our careers and our futures if potential employers discover "inappropriate content" on a candidate's social media sites. This is something that we should keep in mind whenever we share information about ourselves on social media. This "inappropriate material" could consist of things like sexual exposure, intoxication, or the use of profanity, among other things. Evaluation of Facebook pages that include unpleasant content has led to inaccurate

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perceptions about the personality of the person behind the page, according to the conclusions of a research that was conducted on the topic.

Sites of those without an improper appearance led to more accurate judgements on the person's personality; this is something that may make the difference between landing a job or being admitted into a graduate school in the real world (Goodman, Smith, Ivancevich, & Lundberg, 2014).

What Kind of Changes Happen in Our Personality When Social Media Influences It?

The usage of online social networking sites such as Facebook may both form and expose parts of a person's personality, according to research conducted in the field of psychology. Those students who spent an excessive amount of time on the Internet had much greater levels of anxiety and depression, in comparison to their counterparts who spent a far lower total amount of time on the Internet. China provided the participants for the study, who ranged in age from 13 to 18. (Lam & Peng, 2010). Some research has shown that excessive usage of social media may have a detrimental impact on an individual's psychological well-being (how happy we feel) as well as the quality of connections with friends and love partners (Blais, Craig, Pepler, & Connolly, 2008; Huang, 2010a; Kross et al., 2013). In addition, college students who spoke with their parents via social networking sites reported experiencing heightened degrees of loneliness, anxiety, and conflict in their connections with their parents (Gentzler, Oberhauser, Westerman, & Nadorff, 2011).

Those who report using social media platforms to an unhealthy degree have been demonstrated in studies conducted in a broad range of nations such as the Netherlands, Serbia, Hong Kong, and Korea to have poorer levels of self-esteem, as well as feelings of loneliness and introversion. (Baek, Bae, & Jang, 2013; Milosevic-Dordevic & Zezelj, 2013; Muusses, Finkenauer, Kerkhof & Billedo, 2014; Yao & Zhong, 2014). A person may get addicted to the internet if they spend an inordinate amount of time on, and this addiction can be just as obsessive and extreme as an addiction to alcohol, drugs, or gambling. An unhealthy amount of time spent on the internet may eventually lead to addiction. It has also been shown that spending an excessive amount of time online might impact regions of the brain that are related with despondency and heightened

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irritability (Mosher, 2011). Personality and social psychology are two distinct branches of psychology that stem from the same ancestors yet continue to engage in a lively and often contentious dialogue with one another (Pettigrew & Cherry, 2012; Lanning, 2017). Both are diverse and engage in their own arguments within their ranks, but historically speaking, the field has been divided along two distinct worldviews (Cloninger, 2020). The natural sciences approach, which is characterized by the hunt for universal, nomothetic principles to comprehend the links between quantitative elements of individual variation, is the technique that is most often used by researchers looking into personality characteristics (Boyle et al., 2008). They are open to biological explanations for trait variation, such as those offered in studies of evolutionary origins, behavioral and molecular genetics, and neurological research. For example, they are open to the possibility that genes play a role in personality variety. On the other hand, social constructivists are attentive to qualitative and idiographic investigations of the way individuals interact within a certain sociocultural framework. This school of thinking maintains that an individual's personality is continually being negotiated not just "inside" but also "between" other people (Hampson, 1988). They also place a greater value on efforts made by psychologists to promote individual happiness and social justice when seen from the standpoint of natural science, which they feel is more prevalent in the field of psychology (Cloninger, 2020).

Neither point of view can adequately account for everything. On the trait side, for instance, variation in self-related characteristics has been linked to factors associated to motivation and cognition rather than direct neurological impacts. This is the case on the trait side. This is since aspects of one's motivation and cognition are more amenable to change than neurobiological consequences (Ryan & Deci, 2017). The field of experimental social psychology provides a suitable environment for the study of nomothetic theories including those that are oriented on social cognition. But the discord that arises from the clash between naturalistic and scientific viewpoints (Cloninger, 2020) poses a threat to the discipline's internal consistency and coherence.

How Many Different Research Networks Can Collaborate With Each Other More Effectively?

There have been moments of direct rivalry, the most known example of which being Mischel's (1968)'situationist' criticism of personality characteristics. There have also been occasions when competition has been indirect. Because of the differences of opinion shown in this example, high-

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quality research on the topic of inter-situational consistency was generated, which served to bolster an interactive personality model (Funder, 2006). Yet, there is a risk that competition would result in empty rhetoric rather than actual forward movement in scientific research. Trait researchers and social psychologists cohabit rather often; yet they frequently overlook one other's work, which might lead to possibilities for the exchange of ideas being lost. We should consider ourselves fortunate since, over the last several years, there has been a rise in the number of ideas combining the two domains as well as cooperation between the two groups. Often, such endeavors need the unpacking of the component parts that are conceptually distinct for each viewpoint. For instance, social-cognitive theory refers to psychological qualities like self-schema, which, even though they are not a reflection of the actual functioning of the brain, may stay constant throughout the course of one's lifetime. The domains of personality and social psychology face a significant obstacle in the form of the identification of research issues for which it is acceptable to investigate rivalry, cohabitation, and collaboration.

Although it is important that conversations be always held in a civil manner, it's possible that collaboration isn't the answer to all of the problems we face. It is conceivable that one side will have more evidence-based solutions to specific queries than the other party will have. Some topics can only be investigated from a single vantage point, which necessitates the maintenance of peaceful coexistence within an atmosphere devoid of both collaboration and rivalry.

[Lessons that Psychologists Investigating Personality Traits Can Take From Social Psychology](#)

Even if individual variations in social conduct constitute the foundation for many personality qualities — particularly extraversion and agreeableness — the fact that the theory explains so little about what exactly underpins social processes creates a paradox in conventional behavior. With more recent study, this issue has been resolved, and a clearer understanding of the relevance of merging social-psychological theory with trait theory has emerged as a result.

According to studies that examine both behavioral patterns and genetic make-up, at least half of the diversity in significant characteristics may be traced back to the environment, more particularly to "non-shared" variables (Plomin, 2011; Turkheimer et al., 2014).

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It has the potential to help fill in the blanks in our understanding of personality development, which has been left by many other areas of research. The idea that the self is something that is molded by society is something that is common knowledge among social psychologists. Individual variations in the development of self-regulatory skills during infancy influence trait development, and this impact is impacted by socially acceptable reference values or norms. Throughout infancy, self-regulatory capacities have an impact on trait development. This may be viewed in terms of the individual's personality (Denissen et al., 2013). Roberts and Nickel (2017) established a neo-socioanalytic theory that emphasizes investment in social institutions as a driving force for personality development across a person's lifespan. The research that demonstrates the malleability of characteristics in maturity lends credence to this notion. It is not sufficient to assume that an individual's genotype directly feeds into the individual's trait composition because studies have shown that an adequate description of trait development requires specifying how biological and social factors interact dynamically. These studies show that an adequate description of trait development requires this information. According to the research that were referenced, to provide an accurate explanation of trait development, it is necessary to define how biological and social elements interact in a dynamic manner (Matthews, 2016).

Three-Dimensional Organization of Traits Influenced by Culture

One of the fundamental tenets of biological trait theory is the concept that fundamental characteristics, such as the Big Five, remain relatively constant all throughout the globe (Costa and McCrae, 1992). Although though most of the research locate dimensions that are comparable to the Big Five, it is not uncommon for their findings to fall short of achieving the real measurement invariance standards. This is particularly the case in cultures that are neither Western nor industrialized (Church, 2016). The study of personality also uncovers culturally unique characteristics, which are referred to be "emic" or indigenous features. There is a significant window of opportunity for academics interested in personality to investigate the social processes that are responsible for the formation of cultural differences, such as the impact of cultural norms on beliefs, values, and interpersonal communication (Lehman et al., 2004). This is an important opportunity that has arisen because there is a window of opportunity that exists. It is conceivable that gaining an understanding of the disparities that exist between groups and individuals in

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processes of this kind may lead to new insights into the role that gene-culture interactions play in the formation of personality (Church, 2016).

The Significance of Social Context Interactionism has been an essential part of the field of personality research for an exceptionally long time, but traditional biological theories can only consider a constrained range of environmental factors, such as the presence and intensity of both positive and negative reinforcers (Boyle et al., 2008). Research has demonstrated that context-specific indicators, such work self-efficacy and anxieties of assessment, are typically more predictive than general measures. On the other hand, generic measurements are not as predictive as context-specific ones. These research in the realm of personality characteristics provide a challenge to the method that has been taken (Matthews, 2020b).

Conclusion

The discovery of "behavioral signatures" as components of personality coherence is one of the most significant contributions that social psychology has made to the field (Mischel & Shoda, 1995). Behavioral signatures are if-then interactions that establish an individual's usual cognitive, emotional, and behavioral reactions to certain social circumstances. Behavioral signatures may be used to predict an individual's future behavior. Explaining one's identity via the use of narratives offers a supplementary method from a sociological point of view for appreciating the consistency of an individual's personality (McAdams & McLean, 2013). Because of this, the use of the social-psychological viewpoint enhances the capacity of trait models to describe the effect of environmental factors. As a follow-up to the prior point, the social-psychological theory helps to a more comprehensive understanding of the effect of personality characteristics on the subjective experience and conduct of an individual. The social-cognitive self-regulation theories describe processes such as self-affirmation and self-presentation, which can vary consistently among individuals and mitigate the effects of traits. These theories were developed to explain how people can control their behavior in social situations (Robinson & Sedikides, 2020). One illustration of this would be having prior knowledge about unfavorable characteristics of personality, such as neuroticism and trait anxiety. While fundamental brain mechanisms such as sensitivity to punishment do play a part, persons who are strong in these features generally have distinctly social vulnerabilities and uniquely fundamental self-evaluations. This is particularly the case for those

who have an elevated level of these features (Chang et al., 2012). Study that is process-oriented and focuses on key features such as rejection sensitivity helps to better understand how key traits appear in social contexts (Berenson et al., 2009). In a broader sense, social-cognitive theories give a wide range of dynamic process models that are consistent with explanations based on personality characteristics (Cervone, 2005).

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